

Physicochemical Characteristic of Lanthanum and Thorium Soaps

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The infrared spectral studies reveal that the fatty acids exist with dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between two molecules of fatty acids whereas metal-to-oxygen bonds in lanthanide and actinide soaps have an ionic character. The X-ray diffraction results confirm that these soaps have double layer structure with molecular axes slightly inclined to the basal plane. The thermal decomposition of the soaps is found kinetically of zero order and the energy of activation for the process lies in the range 1–10 kcal mol⁻¹. The conductivity results show that the soaps behave as weak electrolyte indicating that the Debye–Hückel–Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions. The viscosity results have been used to test the validity of well-known equations and to determine the CMC of these soaps. The various acoustic parameters have been evaluated from the measurements of ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of these soaps.

A great deal of work has been reported on the alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal soaps but the studies on rare-earth metal soaps remained scanty^{1,2} in spite of their large applications in various industries as emulsifying agents, mordants, water-proofing agents, lubricants, additives and varnish driers.

The present work deals with the studies of lanthanum and thorium soaps in solid state and in solutions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Lanthanum and thorium soaps were prepared by metathesis of sodium soap with an aqueous solution of metal nitrate. The purity of the soaps was checked by elemental analysis and by the determination of melting points.

The ir spectra, X-ray diffraction patterns and thermogravimetric analysis were carried out by the methods reported earlier³. The conductivity, viscosity and ultrasonic measurements for the solutions of soaps in mixtures of benzene and methanol were carried out on Toshniwal CL01.10A conductivity meter, Ostwald viscometer and Ultrasonic Interferometer M-81, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra: The absorption maxima observed near 2 650, 1 700, 1 440, 950, 690 and 550 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of fatty acid are associated with the localised carboxyl group of the acid molecules in the dimeric state and confirm the presence of hydrogen bonds between two molecules of fatty acids. The appearance of two carboxyl bands

corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric stretch of the carboxylate ion at 1 450–1 430 and 1 650–1 540 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of lanthanum and thorium soaps in stead of one band at ~ 1 700 cm⁻¹ confirms that these soaps possess ionised structure and the metal-to-oxygen bonds in these soaps have an ionic character.

X-Ray diffraction: The intensities of diffracted X-rays as a function of diffraction angle, 2θ for lanthanum and thorium caprylates were recorded over the range 6–65°. The interplaner spacings (d) have been calculated from the position of intense peaks using Bragg relationship, $n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$, where λ is the wavelength of radiations.

A large number of peaks arising from the diffraction of X-rays by planes of metal ions (known as basal planes) have been observed in the diffraction pattern of these soaps. The appearance of diffraction upto 13th order for lanthanum caprylate and upto 11th order for thorium caprylate suggests good crystallinity for these soaps. The interplaner spacings (d) calculated for 2nd, 3rd, 6th, 8th, 11th, 12th and 13th order diffractions for lanthanum caprylate are 25.12, 25.14, 25.50, 25.04, 25.00, 24.97 and 24.83 Å, respectively; the average being 25.08 Å. The interplaner spacings calculated for 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 7th, 9th and 11th order diffractions for thorium caprylate are 24.67, 24.98, 24.56, 24.71, 24.77, 24.81 and 25.01 Å, respectively; the average being 24.79 Å. The observed values of long spacing for caprylates (La, 25.08 and Th, 24.79 Å) are smaller than the calculated dimensions of caprylate (27 Å) ions from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles, and this suggests that the molecular axes of these soaps are somewhat inclined to the basal planes. The metal ions fit into spaces

between oxygen atoms of ionised carboxyl group without a large strain of the bonds. On the basis of long spacings, it is proposed that the metal ions in these soaps are arranged in a parallel plane and these soaps have a double layer structure as proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi³.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The results of thermogravimetric analysis are shown in Fig. 1. The final residues are the metal oxides and the weights of the residues are in agreement with the

Fig. 1. Thermograms: (O) lanthanum caprylate and (●) thorium caprylate.

theoretically calculated weights of lanthanum and thorium oxide from the molecular formula of the corresponding soap. A white substance is found condensed at the cold part of the sample tube surrounding the sample and it is identified as

caprylone (m.p. 39°). The thermal decomposition of these soaps can be expressed as

where, R is C₇H₁₅ for caprylate.

It is concluded that the reaction of thermal decomposition of lanthanum and thorium soaps is of zero order and the values of energy of activation obtained from Freeman-Carroll⁴, Horowitz-Metzger⁵ and Coats-Redfern⁶ equations are 9.2, 6.6 and 6.9 kcal mol⁻¹ for lanthanum caprylate and 9.2, 8.6 and 7.7 kcal mol⁻¹ for thorium caprylate.

Conductivity: The specific conductance (*k*) of the solutions of caprylates of lanthanum and thorium in benzene-methanol mixtures of varying compositions increases with the increase in soap concentration (μ) decreases with increasing soap concentration (*C*). The plots of *k* vs *C* show a break at a definite soap concentration¹ (0.0035 *M* for La and 0.0039 *M* for Th) which corresponds to the CMC of these soaps. The concave nature of the plots of μ vs *C*^{1/2} indicates that the soaps behave as weak electrolyte in dilute solution and hence Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions. The limiting molecular conductance (μ₀) have been obtained by developing an expression in Ostwald's manner.

Since these soaps behave as weak electrolytes in dilute solutions, the ionic concentrations are low and the interionic effects may be treated as negligible. Therefore, the dilute soap solutions do not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and the activities of ions can be taken as almost equal to the concentrations. The values of degree of dissociation (α) at different concentrations of the soap have been calculated by assuming it as equal to the conductance ratio, μ/μ₀. The degree of dissociation of these soaps decreases rapidly in dilute solutions with the increase in the soap concentration while it decreases slowly above the CMC. The values of

TABLE I—CONDUCTIVITY, VISCOSITY AND ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF LANTHANUM CAPRYLATE IN 1 : 1 BENZENE-METHANOL AT 40±0.05°

Sl. no	Concn. g mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁶ Ω ⁻¹	ρ g ml ⁻¹	η × 10 ³ poise	<i>v</i> × 10 ⁻³ m s ⁻¹	β × 10 ¹⁰ m ³ N	φ _v dm ³ mol ⁻¹	<i>L</i> _t × 10 ⁻¹¹ m	<i>Z</i> × 10 ⁸ (MKS unit)	Molar sound velocity m s ⁻¹	<i>S</i> _n
1.	0.001 2	9.49	0.831 1	4.870	1.125	9.50	-3.93	6.25	9.34	27.294	54.03
2.	0.001 4	9.88	0.832 3	4.876	1.128	9.44	-4.08	6.23	9.38	27.335	54.04
3.	0.001 8	10.62	0.834 4	4.912	1.133	9.34	-4.27	6.20	9.44	27.426	52.07
4.	0.002 2	11.39	0.838 2	4.924	1.139	9.22	-4.39	6.16	9.52	27.518	52.46
5.	0.002 6	12.23	0.839 0	4.967	1.146	9.07	-4.94	6.11	9.61	27.592	52.80
6.	0.003 3	13.38	0.844 2	4.996	1.155	8.86	-5.49	6.04	9.74	27.696	52.67
7.	0.004 0	14.33	0.853 6	5.075	1.160	8.71	-7.06	5.99	9.90	27.688	51.87
8.	0.004 9	15.48	0.865 7	5.146	1.166	8.50	-8.53	5.91	10.08	27.550	50.08
9.	0.006 2	17.21	0.881 2	5.268	1.175	8.22	-9.73	5.82	10.35	27.469	47.74
10.	0.008 3	20.44	0.907 3	5.504	1.190	7.78	-10.70	5.66	10.79	27.348	45.23
11.	0.010 0	24.98	0.928 9	5.631	1.203	7.74	-11.24	5.53	11.16	27.262	43.68

dissociation constant, K vs soap concentration, C show an approximate constancy in dilute solutions but exhibit a drift with the increase in the soap concentration, indicating that the soap does not behave as a very weak electrolyte. The drift in the values of K may partly be due to the fact that the degree of dissociation (α) is not equal to the conductance ratio (μ/μ_0) but mainly due to the fact that the activity coefficients of ions are not equal to unity at higher concentrations.

The conductivity results of these soaps in benzene-methanol mixtures of varying compositions (10-90%) are in agreement with the results in 50% benzene and methanol mixture.

Viscosity: Viscosity (η) of the solutions of lanthanum and thorium soaps in 1:1 benzene-methanol increases with increasing soap concentration, C (Table 1). The increase in viscosity may be due to the increasing tendency of these soaps to form aggregates at higher concentration. The plots of η vs C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap indicating a marked change in the aggregation of the soap molecules at the CMC.

The viscosity data have been used to test the validity of Einstein⁷, Vand⁸, Moulik⁹ and Jones-Dole¹⁰ equations. The values of molar volume, \bar{V} (lanthanum caprylate, 7.2 and thorium caprylate, 8.6 dm³ mol⁻¹) calculated from Einstein equation are in fair agreement with the values (lanthanum caprylate, 7.4 and thorium caprylate, 9.1 dm³ mol⁻¹) obtained from Vand equation. The values of Jones-Dole constant indicate that the soap-solvent interaction (lanthanum caprylate, 22 and thorium caprylate, 28) is greater than the soap-soap interaction (lanthanum caprylate, -0.02 and thorium caprylate, 0.0).

Ultrasonic measurements: The ultrasonic velocity (v) in the solutions of lanthanum and thorium soaps in 1:1 benzene-methanol increases with the increase in the soap concentration (Table 1). The plots of v vs C indicate a break at a soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap (La, 0.0035 and Th, 0.0038 M).

The adiabatic compressibility (β) and intermolecular free length (L_t) decrease while specific acoustic impedance increases with the increase in soap concentration. The adiabatic compressibility of the solutions of lanthanum and thorium soaps is found to obey Bachem relation,

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2}$$

where, β_0 is the compressibility of the solvent. The values of A and B have been calculated from the intercept and slope of the linear plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs $C^{1/2}$. The values are found to be A , -20.5,

-30.3, and B , 111.0 and 92.2 for La and thorium soaps, respectively.

The variation of apparent molal volume (ϕ_v), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_k), molar sound velocity (R) and solvation number (S_n) with soap concentration is linear which is in agreement with the results of other workers¹¹. The decrease in adiabatic compressibility, apparent molal volume and intermolecular free length and increase in specific acoustic impedance of the soap solutions with increasing concentration may be explained on the basis of the fact that the ions in solutions are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules firmly bound and oriented towards ions. The orientation of the solvent molecules around the ions may be due to the influence of electrostatic field of ions and results in the increase in internal pressure and in lowering of the compressibility of the solutions, i.e. solutions become harder to compress. This indicates that there is a significant soap-solvent interaction due to which the structural arrangement is considerably affected.

It is concluded, therefore, that these soaps in dilute solutions behave as a weak electrolyte and they exhibit soap-solvent interactions.

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